

LINGUISTIC COMPARISON OF RHETORICAL SENTENCES IN THREE LANGUAGES: ENGLISH, UZBEK AND RUSSIAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7430701>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 29th November 2022

Accepted: 11th December 2022

Online: 12th December 2022

KEY WORDS

Rhetorical expression,
rhetorical complex;
interrogative form; expressivity,
interrogative sentence, rhetoric,
rhetorical question, stylistic
figures

ABSTRACT

The given article deals with the features of rhetorical interrogative sentences in English, Uzbek and Russian which are widely used in various genres of both oral and written speech of the compared languages. The types of interrogative propositions are analyzed depending on the content of the question, and the most common rhetorical questions are also discussed, since in the system of interrogative sentences, rhetorical interrogative sentences have a special meaning both in grammatical, logical, and stylistic terms.

The given research is also aimed to review the functions of rhetorical expressions in different patterns of the public speech. The author singles out the function of exposure as the main function. The article is also devoted to the analysis of subjective-emotional side of the expression.

Introduction

A rhetorical statement in this article is understood as a statement that has an interrogative form (pronominal components, interrogative particles, interrogative intonation), but does not imply a response verbal reaction of the addressee. In rhetoric, such statements are defined as a rhetorical question. The well-known Russian scientist, the author of the "General Rhetoric" in 1844 N. Koshansky, referring the rhetorical question to the figures of thought, noted that the figures of thoughts deviate from "simple, ordinary, cold speech", that they are "an expression full of feelings - the language of passions". The speaker uses figures of thoughts "in

the heat of feelings, in the striving of the soul, in the ardent movement of the heart" [Koshansky 1844]. The rhetorical statements used on the modern newspaper page (hereinafter - RV) do not have those specific features that were inherent in them initially, when they served as a means of conveying lofty feelings, noble impulses, passion, pathos. Of the many functions of PR (emotive, evaluative, influencing, argumentative, appellative, etc.) in the modern press, the function of exposing, convicting people known to the general public in unseemly acts predominates. The attention of the writers is focused on scandalous, criminal, illegal, immoral acts. The authors of the articles do not hesitate

in expressions and straightforward assessments, acting as irreconcilable opponents of those who are criticized. Reading the articles by A. Prokhanov, V. Kostikov, one involuntarily shrinks from the seething rage, hatred of the authors, and at the same time one feels a sense of awkwardness: there is no culture of public speaking, a culture of communication. And isn't this a belated revelation?

The functions of exposure are especially subject to rhetorical statements used by politicians who are in opposition to the current power structures of different levels. These RVs have a pronounced emotional character: indignation, contempt, mockery, sarcasm, and so on. Authors of public speeches bring down a negative emotional mood on their opponents by means of RW, appealing to the consciousness and feelings of the addressee, wanting to influence in the right direction the opinions and assessments formed by the listener. Passion, emotional intensity, rigidity of assessments are distinguished, for example, by V. Kostikov's public speeches.

Main part

The author is not limited to the field of sports when he talks about the misuse of financial budgetary funds. RS with pronominal components where, why and verbal predicates to get away (disappear, abyss) in the form of the perfect past determine the position of the author, reflected in the question.

pleading form: Questions of this kind stir in all the nooks and crannies of the economy. Where, for example, have gone the 3 billion rubles embezzled, according to Chief Military Prosecutor S. Fridinsky, in the country's law enforcement agencies? It

is clear that they did not get to ordinary soldiers and junior officers

whether. Accusatory pathos, emotion of indignation, negative evaluation are reinforced by the lexical repetition of why. All co-components of a rhetorical statement are aimed at the pragmatic effect of public speaking, increasing its subjectivity. The addressee also has a question: "Really, why?" The final rhetorical statement in this block with a particle is not ... is it an affirmative sentence of "operational preference" [Arutyunova 1998]. It reflects the author's position: doesn't better mean better. The axiological setting of the author, his value orientation is also expressed in the following rhetorical statements: Recently we went to a friend's dacha along Rublevsky highway towards Zvenigorod. And here we go: no fields, no forests, there are 6-meter fences on both sides of the road. Who are they hiding from? From nature? From cranes in the sky? Have you seen this anywhere abroad? Such laconic rhetorical sentences sometimes affect the addressee more than some lengthy dispassionate texts.

Rhetorical statements with particles are common in the modern press, really and perhaps. Their semantics in the most general form is an expression of the inconsistency of the author's position with a different version or interpretation of the event: "... the content of the sentence with the particle does not contradict the positive information that the speaker previously had, and the content of the sentence with the particle "really" - his hypotheses, which he is inclined to put forward, but about the truth of which he has no positive data" [Bulygina, Shmelev 1997].

Thus, the journalist Leonid Mlechin, speaking about the reasons for Major Evsyukov's "revelry", which led to the death of people, writes: "Dangerous inclinations could not but manifest themselves before. Did no one notice anything? Or do people with these qualities just find themselves in the police? Does the RE with a particle really express the semantics of the statement, the author's confidence in the opposite: It cannot be that no one notices anything. The rhetorical form of the statement also includes the author's harsh mockery. The second rhetorical statement is also sarcastic. A rhetorical statement with the particle "unless" through a negative form asserts a different proposition, namely, what qualities young people who join law enforcement agencies should have: "Are young people who come to law enforcement agencies taught to protect and protect citizens? Is it possible that when they are sent to patrol the city, they are told: help people, protect them from trouble? They are taught something completely different: to seize and disperse, to imprison and punish." Emphasizing the cause-and-effect relationship, the author uses a rhetorical sentence of a complex structure: Police chiefs are built into the system of general corruption. And the ordinary policeman sees everything: if the general built a mansion and drives a Mercedes, why shouldn't he get his share? And he eventually gets it.

Interrogative sentences play a special role in the system of communicative types of speech. The fact is that interrogative sentences represent a request for reality unknown to the speaker. Such phrases are built on special words and are pronounced

separately, with a question mark at the end of the sentence.

The question is most often used in the form of a dialogue.[1] An interrogative sentence is divided into three types depending on the content of the question expressed in it:

a) соф сўроқ гаплар (interrogative sentences)

Kim chaqiryapti? (кто зовёт?) Who is calling?

b) So'roq-buyruq gaplar (interrogative-imperative sentences)

Tezroq yura olasizmi? (вы можете побыстрее ходить?) Can you walk quickly?

c) Ritorik so'roq gaplar. (rhetorical-interrogative sentences)

"If your friend jumped off the bridge would you do it too?

Agar sherigingiz o'zini ko'prikdan tashlasa siz ham tashlaysizmi?

Если ваш друг прыгнет с моста вы тоже прыгнете?"

In the system of interrogative sentences, rhetorical interrogative sentences have a special meaning both in grammatical, logical and stylistic terms. In a rhetorical interrogative sentence, it is usually understood that the answer is also inside the question and is used as a stylistic tool in emotional (affective) speech. In this task, the rhetorical question, when used as a stylistic tool, does not require any answer, albeit in the form of questions, but is used to emphasize the information expressed in the question and receive it.

listener approval.[2]

This is why in some cases rhetorical questions are not made at the end of a sentence. Rhetorical interrogative sentences are often used as a means to

start a conversation with an interlocutor or as a means of attracting

the speaker's attention to the problem without requiring a direct answer. As one of the most common rhetorical questions in English:

"Can't you do anything right?" (Can't you do something right?)

Kўlingizdan biron-bir foidali ish keladimi, ʻzi?) The speaker does not ask if the listener is capable of doing something useful, but is used to emphasize his inferiority. Rhetorical questions often reflect a challenge that cannot be answered. Thus, the rhetorical interrogative sentence appears as a confirmation of the negation. For example:

What have the Romans ever done for us? (MontyPython). An interrogative sentence is used to express the meaning "Rimliklar biz uchun nima qilib qiypti? ("what the Romans did for us, that is, "The Romans have never done anything for us" (the Romans never did anything for us). Similarly, from the work of W. Shakespeare's work "Julius Caesar" Mark Antony:

- Here was a Caesar! When comes such another?

- Here was Caesar! When will this one come? (Buerda Julius Caesar bulgan! Yana bunakasi kachon keladi?) And indicates that he has a rare ability that is rarely found in others, and that such a person will not be born soon?

Conclusion

In the conclusion I would like to assume that rhetorical questioning is used as a stylistic tool to increase the sensitivity of an event or information in various genres of speech and writing, especially in poetry. This is often used as a metaphor for the issue mentioned in the text.

This type of rhetorical question is often referred to as "narrative rhetorical" and the answer to this question is determined by another humorous question. For example,

Is the sky blue?

- Is the sun hot?

-- Is the Pope Catholic?

Some rhetorical interrogative preburns have become idiomatic compounds in English. For example:

- What's the matter with you?

- Sizga nima bouldi? Tuppa-tuzuk edingizku? (What's wrong with you?)

- Don't you know any better?

- Tuzukroq zhavobingiz yўkmi? (Can't you answer better?)

- Have you no shame?

- Uyalmaysizmi? (Aren't you ashamed?)

- Are you crazy?

- Ginnimisi? (You're a fool?)

- How should I know?

- Men kayodan bilay? (How should I know?)

There are a number of stylistic figures in modern English, such as litote, antithesis, polysyndetone, asinetone, and climax, which often take an active part in rhetorical interrogative sentences. One of the most common of these is the litote.[1]

It is well known that in English negation can only be expressed by one means. The stylistic figure called Litota raises a rhetorical question, expressing discourse through double negation. For example:

Not bad." - "Good. Yomon emas - Yahshi. (Not bad - Good)

It is no ordinary city. - It is a very impressive city.

Not just ordinary cities - this is a very interesting city.

That sword was not useless to the warrior now. - The warrior has a use for the sword now. This sword was not useless to the warrior now. - It is necessary for a warrior. She is not as young as she was. - She's old.

Bu ayol avvalgidek yosh emas. - Ancha keksayibdi.

She was not as young as she was. - she's getting older

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